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WORK RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS IN AGRICULTURE WORKERS

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OVERVIEW

The word agriculture is derived from Latin words 'Ager or Agri meaning Soil' and 'Culture meaning, Cultivation'. The science and art of cultivation on the soil, raising crops and rearing livestock. It is also called farming. Agriculture is a primary activity. Primary activities include all those connected with extraction and production of natural resources. Agriculture, fishing and gathering are good examples. Sustainability in agriculture results in improvement in human life, environment, economy, workers rights, and use of resources. [1]

Figure 1 Triangle of sustainability

AGRICULTURE AND ITS PRACTICES

Farming System is defined as a complex inter related matrix of soil, plants, animals, implements, power, labour capital and other inputs controlled in part by farming families and influenced to varying degrees by political, economic, institutional and social forces that operate at many levels. The important inputs are seeds, fertilizers, machinery and labour. Labour includes ploughing, sowing, weeding, transplanting, irrigation, harvesting, cultivation, forestry, plantation, fisheries, and others as principal agricultural operations. The outputs from the system includes crops, wool, dairy and poultry products. [4] [5]

World distribution of arable land, 2018

Figure 2 Arable land, 2018

Figure 2:(<https://ourworldindata.org/land-use>)

● Types of Farming

Farming is practice in many ways across the world. Depending upon the geographical conditions, demand of produce, labour and level of technology, farming can be classified into two types. These are subsistence farming and commercial farming.

1) Subsistence Farming

- + Intensive subsistence agriculture
- + Primitive subsistence agriculture
- + Shifting cultivation
- + Nomadic herding

2) Commercial Farming

- + Commercial grain farming
- + Mixed farming
- + Plantations

● Categories of farmers

1. Non waged Farmers : Large - large and middle scale farmers, small scale farmers, subsistence farmers, unpaid family workers, collective farmers
2. Waged Farmers : Permanent workers, Temporary and seasonal workers, Migrant workers, Subcontracted workers, Informal sector

● Farming method

According to type of holdings and its production technique

1. Micro holdings (a very limited area)
 - + Subsistence agriculture
2. Small holdings (under 10 Ha)
 - + Traditional methods, small-cattle raising, small local marketable surplus
3. Middle-sized farms (10 to 50 Ha)
 - + Traditional methods and semi-mechanized agriculture, small-cattle raising, national and international marketable production
4. Large farms (50 to 500 Ha)
 - + Advanced mechanized agriculture with

great use of chemicals intensive and extensive industrial agriculture cattle raising, national and international marketable production

5. Larger farms (above 500 Ha)

- ✦ Advanced mechanized agriculture with great use of chemicals intensive and extensive industrial

● Employment in Agriculture, 2019

Figure 3 Employment in Agriculture
Figure 3 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.AGR.EMPL.ZS?view=map&year=2019>

AGRICULTURE AS A PROFESSION

Agriculture is considered to be one of the oldest occupations perhaps as old as human civilization. Agriculture workers are the main pillars for growth and development of this sector. An estimated 1.3 billion workers are active in agricultural production worldwide. Agriculture still forms the backbone of the Indian economy. Economic endeavor that utilizes directly the natural resources of soil and water for production is included in agriculture. It plays the vital role for socio-economic development. It determines the health of the people as well as wealth of the nation. Agriculture involves the use of a wide

variety of hazardous machinery and processes. Among the most common are tractors, cultivators, harrows, seeding equipment, sprayers, harvesters, mowers, balers, grinders, trucks, wagons, trailers, all-terrain vehicles, augers, manure spreaders, and elevating equipment. [2] [5] Agriculture activities being most unorganized and very less attentive. Health problems of agriculture workers includes accidents (machine injuries, snake and insect bites), toxic hazards (chemical exposures and insecticide poisoning), physical hazards (extreme conditions, solar radiation), and respiratory problems (farmer's lung, occupational asthma)

● WORK RELATED MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS

There are two components the muscular system and the skeletal system. Musculoskeletal disorders are injuries and illnesses that affect bones, spinal discs, joints, ligaments, cartilage, blood vessels, nerves, tendons, muscle and compromise their function. Work related musculoskeletal disorders are a major cause of workers impairment, disability and compensation in agriculture. The pathogenesis of these disorders is not fully understood, but it appears to involve the exposure to certain external physical stressors. It has been proposed that these external stressors produce a series of internal biomechanical and physiologic disturbances. Physical stressors

are related to work requirements, such as production standards and work equipment, and to individual factors, such as body size and capacity. [3] [6]

AGRICULTURAL RISK FACTORS

• Occupational physical risk factors:

Upper extremity musculoskeletal disorders associated with Forceful hand and arm exertions, repetitive upper extremity activity, postural discomfort, static postures and vibration. For example shoulder disorders, lateral epicondylitis, carpal tunnel syndrome, hand/wrist tendinitis, hand-arm vibration syndrome

Occupational risk factors associated with low back disorders include lifting, forceful

movements, heavy physical work, static work postures such as stooping, whole body vibration and awkward postures such as twisting and bending. [10]

Psychosocial factors may be important in the development of musculoskeletal disorders and the likelihood that a disability may occur. Job stressors such as workload, lack of job control and job future ambiguity can produce stress responses that increase the potential for musculoskeletal disorders. [9]

• Non occupational risk factors:

Factors include pre-existing rheumatologic disease, history of musculoskeletal disorder and at least for carpal tunnel syndrome, body mass index, pregnancy, diabetes, renal dialysis and thyroid disease

• Pathophysiology of Work related musculoskeletal disorders

Figure 5 A conceptual model of various factors in the development of musculoskeletal disorders

WMSDs has a gradual onset as compared to an acute injury. The term 'load' is frequently used to describe the physical stresses acting on the body and structures within the body. These stresses include kinetic (force), kinematic (motion), oscillatory (vibration), and thermal (temperature) energy sources. There are two categories in the model, workplace factors and characteristics of the individual. The dotted box outline on the right indicates the possible pathways and processes that could occur within the person, including the biomechanical load-tolerance relationship and

the factors that may mediate the load-tolerance relationship, such as individual factors and adaptation. [10] Outcomes is a result of this relationship may be influenced by individual factors, such as conditioning or psychological state. The dotted box on the left indicates the possible influences of the workplace on the sequence of events that can lead to musculoskeletal disorders in the person. Arrows between 'the workplace' factors and 'the person' box indicate the various research disciplines (epidemiology, biomechanics, physiology, etc.) [1] [11]

• **Relationships between external and internal physical stress**

Physical Stress	Property (* indicates internal physical stress)		
	Magnitude	Repetition	Duration
Force	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Tissue loads and stress ✦ Muscle tension and contraction ✦ Joint loads ✦ Transmission of vibrational energy ✦ Adjacent anatomical structure loads and compartment pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Tissue loading rate and energy storage ✦ Tissue strain recovery ✦ Muscle fiber recruitment and muscle fatigue rate ✦ Energy expenditure, fatigue and elimination of metabolites ✦ Cartilage or disc rehydration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Cumulative tissue loads ✦ Muscle fiber recruitment and muscle fatigue rate ✦ Energy expenditure, fatigue and metabolite production
Motion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Tissue loads and stress ✦ Adjacent anatomical structure loads and compartment pressure ✦ Transmission of vibrational energy* 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Tissue loading rate and energy storage ✦ Tissue strain recovery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Cumulative tissue loads
Vibration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Transmission of vibrational energy to musculoskeletal system ✦ Transmission of energy to somatic and autonomic sensory receptors and nerves ✦ Transmission of energy to muscle spindles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Recovery from vibrational energy exposure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Cumulative vibrational energy exposure
Cold	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Thermal energy loss from the extremities ✦ Somatic & autonomic receptor stimulus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Recovery from thermal energy loss 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✦ Cumulative thermal energy loss

The Occupational Safety and Health Administration given three tiers ergonomic solutions.

Engineering controls, in which employers physically change the worker's relationship to the work.

Changing the way materials, parts, and products can be transported. For example, using material handling devices to relieve heavy load lifting and carrying tasks, or using handles or slotted hand holes in packages requiring manual handling.

Changing the way materials, parts, and products can be transported. For example, using material handling devices to relieve heavy load lifting and carrying tasks, or using handles or slotted hand holes in packages requiring manual handling

Changing workstation layout, which might include using height adjustable work benches or locating tools and materials within short reaching distances

Changing how parts, tools, and materials are to be manipulated for examples include using clamps to reduce the strain of static grasping on the hands and arms.

Changing tool designs for example, longer handles on tools to minimize stooping or reaching

Administrative control strategies include changes in job procedures such as scheduling more rest breaks, rotating workers through tasks, training workers to recognize ergonomic risk factors and to learn techniques for reducing the stress. Some examples of administrative controls are, reduce shift length or curtailing the amount of overtime. Rotate workers through several jobs with different physical demands to reduce the stress on limbs and body regions. Schedule more breaks to allow for rest and recovery. Broaden the job content to offset certain risk factors (e.g. repetitive motions, static and awkward postures). Adjust the work pace to relieve

repetitive motion risks and give the worker more control of the work process. Train in the recognition of risk factors for WMSDs and instruction in work practices that can ease the task demands or burden.

Personal protective equipment, such as wrist supports, back belts, or vibration attenuation gloves, respirators, ear plugs, safety goggles, safety shoes are effective.

CONCLUSION

Farmers are susceptible to occupational health risks. Musculoskeletal disorders are a major concern globally not just due to the pain and disability suffered by the individual workers but also due to occupational stress. As a result, the workplace risk factors associated with the occurrence of musculoskeletal disorders of the upper extremities are expected to increase.

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